

Polymer based thermosensitive in-situ hydrogel in ophthalmic drug delivery

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Introduction

As distinctive anatomy of eye restricts the admittance of drug into ocular tissue so it is very challenging task for scientist to target eye tissue for drug delivery. Eye drop is the highly effective and widely acceptable form for treating a number of eye diseases as drug can be instilled very easily through eye drop. But due to rapid lachrymal elimination, drainage and tear turn over, only 1-5% of instilled drug is absorbed by ocular surface and in addition, systemic absorption of a major portion of the drug may cause undesirable toxic effects¹⁻⁵. To attain desired therapeutic effect either frequent instillation of drug dose is required or it is necessary to apply concentrated drug solution. However, they could have harmful side effects and damage cells in ocular tissue. To get better ocular bioavailability of the inserted drug and delay the rate of drug diffusion, several types of delivery systems, including viscous solutions, premade hydrogels, ointments, polymeric inserts, suspensions, etc., have been investigated. However, these ocular delivery methods cannot be employed widely due to patient noncompliance, hazy vision, and eye discomfort⁶⁻⁷.

Characteristics of an ideal ocular drug delivery system⁸:

1. Sufficient corneal infiltration.
2. Ease in administering.
3. Ideal in drop structure.
4. Decreased instillation frequency.
5. Permissible to Patient.
6. Increasing ocular medication assimilation through extended contact with corneal tissue
7. Least toxic and side effect.
8. Continued drug discharge rate.

9. Non-irritating and comfy forms (viscous solution should not promote lachrymal discharge and rapid blinking of eye).
10. The vision should not be blurred.
11. Suitable rheological features and concentration of viscous system

In light of this, the fabrication of an in situ forming hydrogel system is considered as the best way out for the aforementioned issues.

Figure 1: Benefits of the liquid state and gel state of in-situ gelling ophthalmic delivery system

What is hydrogel?

Hydrogels are made of hydrophilic polymeric network having three dimensional cross-links. It can swell drastically by attracting extremely huge quantity of water without disintegrating into it⁹⁻¹⁰. Hydrogel is suitable for many biological applications, including controlled drug administration, because of its physically attractive and tunable features¹¹.

What is in-situ hydrogel?

In situ hydrogel systems comprising of a mixture of drug and polymeric material and undergo in situ phase transition on the instillation side of the body. For the fabrication of in situ gelling drug delivery formulations, both natural and manufactured polymers are utilized¹². Throughout the past several years, in situ forming gelling systems exhibited numerous potentials for several biomedical uses like drug delivery, injectable implant, tissue repair and so on¹³⁻¹⁷. The way of designing in situ gel based ophthalmic drug delivery systems will be such that they are in the fluid condition during instillation but instantly converted into gel state when in contact with eye surface. This allows them to achieve sustained drug release rates¹⁸.

Figure 2: in-situ gelling procedure on ocular surface

This gelation process of the hydrogel is stimulated by different stimulant of body like temperature, pH or ionic medium. Polymers like Poloxamers, methyl cellulose, xyloglucan, poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) have temperature responsive or thermoresponsive gelation property and temperature of eye environment can cause in situ gel formation of these polymers, whereas gellan gum, kappa-carrageenan, low methoxy pectins, alginic acid can form gel while in

contact with the constituent ions (Na^+ , Ca^{2+}) of tear fluid. Poly acrylic acid (PAA), poly (N, N-diethylamino ethylmethacrylate) (PDEMA) experience gelation transition at certain pH value¹⁹⁻²¹.

Figure 3: Hydrogel as sustained ocular drug delivery systems.

Advantages of In-situ gelling ophthalmic drug delivery systems²²:

- Drug excretion continues for long period and keeping up generally steady plasma profile.
- Little or no obscured vision when contrasted with ointments.
- Improved ocular bioavailability because of extended precorneal contact time and absorption.
- Probability of drug drainage through nasolacrimal route decreases, therefore wastage of drug as well as unpleasant side effects decreases.
- Exact and reproducible amount of drug is possible to instill in contrast to preformed hydrogel formulations.
- Frequent dosing is not necessary and therefore enhances compliance as well as comfort of patient.

- Provide more comfort than insoluble or soluble insertion.

Polymers used in in-situ gelling system:

Various polymers are utilized to design *in situ* gelling framework and they may be categorized by their source and gelation process.

Perfect nature of polymers utilized for in-situ gelling frameworks²³:

- It needs to be biologically permeable and nontoxic.
- It ought to have suitable mucoadhesion nature.
- It ought to have fluidity that is pseudo plastic in nature.
- It ought to be well acceptable to eye.
- It ought to have great optical activity.
- It should control the tear behavior.
- With growing sheer rate the polymer is desired to be capable of reducing the viscosity.

Table 1: List of the utilizing polymers in in-situ gelling strategies²⁴

Polymer	Origin	Charge	Solubility	Mucoadhesive Capacity	Mechanism of Gelation
Carbomer	Synthetic	Anionic	Insoluble	+++	pH
Polyacrylic acid	Natural	Anionic	Insoluble	+++	pH
Chitosan	Natural	Cationic	Soluble	++	pH
Gellan Gum	Natural	Anionic	soluble	++	Ion
Sodium alginate	Natural	Anionic	Soluble	++	Ion
Methyl Cellulose	Natural	Neutral	Soluble	+	Temperature
Xyloglucan	Natural	Anionic	Soluble	+	Temperature
Poloxamer	Synthetic	Non-ionic	Soluble	++	Temperature
HPMC	Natural	Non-ionic	Soluble	+	Temperature

Table 2: Market available product of in situ polymeric system²⁵

Product Name	Drug Used in the Formulation	Manufacturing Company
Timoptic-XE	Timolol maleate	Merck and Co.Inc.
Regel depot-technology	Human Growth Hormone	Macromed
Cytoryn	Interleukin-2(IL-2)	Macromed
Azasite	Azithromycin	InSite Vision
Pilopine HS	Pilocarpine hydrochloride	Alcon Laboratories Inc.
AktenTM	Lidocaine hydrochloride	Akten
Virgan	Ganciclovir Spectrum	Thea Pharmaceuticals

Temperature responsive in-situ gelling polymer:

Polymer employed for the construction of temperature responsive in situ gelling ophthalmic delivery systems are poloxamer, different cellulose derivatives and xyloglucan, chitosan. These polymer solutions provide sustained drug delivery by changing themselves into gel state from sol state at the eye temperature. The following figure shows the mechanism of temperature sensitive gel formation:

Figure 4: Mechanism of gelation of in-situ gelling system²⁶

Poloxamers (Pluronic):

Poloxamer 407 is a synthetic triblock copolymer of poly (ethylene oxide)-b-poly (propylene oxide)-b-poly (ethylene oxide) (PEO-PPO-PEO) having following structure:

Poloxamer 407

Poloxamer 407 is extensively applied as ophthalmic drug delivery vehicle for its water soluble nature, low toxicity and transparent gel formation ability which can not obscure normal vision. They dissolve in cold water and 18 wt% aqueous solutions develop transparent gel at physiological temperature. Actually, when the temperature rises, the hydrophilic PEO unit gradually dehydrated and gelation take place as a result of increased micellar aggregation and increased entanglement between polymer networks²⁷. There are four grade of poloxamers that are often used: 188 (F-68), 237 (F-87), 338 (F-108) and 407 (F-127)²⁸.

Cellulose derivatives:

Several cellulose derivatives, including methyl cellulose (MC), sodium carboxymethyl cellulose (NaCMC), hydroxyethyl cellulose (HEC), and hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose (HPMC) have

thermoreversible gelation property and are generally employed in ophthalmic drug delivery formulation. Lower concentration of these polymer solutions (1-10%) converted to gel state on heating.

1 to 2% solution of methyl cellulose is utilized in ophthalmic drug delivery system because it is low viscous liquid and easy to instill but form gel at 50 to 60°C. It is applied as viscosity modifier. HPMC of 3-4% concentration form gel at 75-90°C²⁹. Their higher gelation temperature is adjusted to physiological temperature by physical or chemical modification. Gelation temperature of MC is lowered to body temperature by adding salt. Whereas gelation temperature of HPMC can be modified by decreasing molar substitution of hydroxypropyl group²⁶. Due to swelling and erosion in eye environment, MC gel is not required to remove after entire drug release. HPMC have highly mucoadhesive property for which it can bind the mucus layer of

ocular tissue and delayed drug release rate. So HPMC is highly utilized by researchers as mucoadhesive polymer for controlled drug delivery vehicle³⁰.

Xyloglucan:

Xyloglucan (also known as Tamarind seeds polysaccharide) is a polysaccharide that is derived from tamarind seeds (TSP). It is highly water soluble and its diluted aqueous solution exhibit thermoreversible gelation only when partial degradation occurred by β -galactosidase and the galactose elimination ratio exceeds $\sim 35\%$. It has been reported in many studies that TSP gels may be used for rectal, ophthalmic, intraperitoneal, and oral drug delivery²⁹.

Preparation of Temperature responsive in-situ gel formulation:

The concentration of the polymer to be used for in situ gel formulation should be such that the solution should behave as free flowing liquid in room temperature but must form gel instantly as soon as it is dropped into eye. These entire polymers, discussed above, selected for in-situ gel formulation are water soluble. So preparation procedure is very simple.

The poloxamer 407 (PM) solutions are prepared by dissolving the required amount in distilled, deionized cold water ($\sim 4^{\circ}\text{C}$) with continuous stirring until a clear solution is obtained.

Figure 5: Schematic flow chart of the solution preparation.

For the preparation of methyl cellulose (MC) or hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose (HPMC) solutions, specific amount and specific grade of MC or HPMC are mixed with distilled, deionized water and stirred continuously until dissolved and kept in a refrigerator for 48 h.

Xyloglucan solution can also be prepared in very simple way by slowly adding the required amount of the polymer to cold distilled water and the mixture is slowly homogenized.

In case of most of the polymer used for ophthalmic drug delivery formulation are soluble in cold water. Formulations are prepared by dissolving the polymers in cold water. In case of chitosan based ophthalmic formulation, chitosan is dissolved in 0.5% acetic acid.

Research development in thermo-responsive in situ polymeric gelsystems for ocular drug delivery application:

Over the past few decades several thermoreversible in-situ gel formulations have been designed by researchers to achieve sustained ocular drug release rate. We have mentioned here some of that.

Li et al have created ophthalmic in-situ gel formulations of Brinzolamide drug resin by combining poloxamer 407 with carbopol 934P and sodium alginate separately and proved that their optimal formulations have better drug retaining ability in compare to commercial drug formulation³¹.

Khateb et al. also looked at the rate at which ofloxacin was released from an in-situ gelling system that contained sodium alginate and the poloxamer analogues (PF-127 and PF-68) and proved that their formulations were non-irritant to eye and have superior retention capacity³². Cellulose derivatives have been used as additives to increase ocular bioavailability of poloxamer in situ hydrogels. The mucoadhesive power of poloxamer hydrogels has been significantly improved by the addition of HPMC, and the rate of drug release has been slowed³³. Bain et al. have designed a series of in situ ketorolac tromethamine ophthalmic drug delivery vehicle based on methyl cellulose. They used salts of different concentration to decrease the gelation temperature to body temperature. Their formulations have also increased the drug release time. Bhowmick et al., used i-carrageenan with potassium chloride salt which was effective to decrease the gelation temperature of the 1% MC solution from 60 °C to 33.5 °C and improve drug retaining capacity³⁴⁻³⁶. Gratieri et al. and Moyal et al. have proved that combining poloxamer analogues with a mucoadhesive polymer like chitosan or hyaluronic acid can also increase the retention period of drug for ocular therapy by improving mechanical strength and texture properties of gel³⁷⁻³⁸.

Besides poloxamer, Poly (N-isopropylacrylamide) (PN) is also a vastly employed thermoresponsive polymer. Hsiue et al. have generated linear PN and crosslinked PN nanoparticles based ophthalmic formulation containing Epinephrine drug. They proved that their developed formulations lasted for longer period than the conventional eye drop³⁹.

Table 3: A few instances of thermosensitive In-situ gelling systems

Sample Drugs	Polymer	Major Observation	Reference
Ketorolac Tromethamine (KT)	Poloxamer 407 and Methyl Cellulose	The formulation restricts the release of KT over a period of 9h.	40
Atropine Sulphate	Poloxamer 407 and mixture of Xanthan gum & guar gum	The formulation form gel at ~32°C and in vivo study on rabbit proved that the designed formulation is helpful in retaining drug for	41

		extended period of time	
Ketorolac Tromethamine (KT)	Methyl cellulose, fructose & sodium citrate tribasic dihydrate	The developed formulation's gelation temperature was 32°C, and it offers a sustained release time of more than 9 hours.	42
Indomethacine	Xyloglucan	The sustained release activities of Indomethcin proved by <i>in vitro</i> study and <i>in vivo</i> study is more satisfactory than commercial suppositories.	43
Timol maleate	Poly(N-isopropyl acrylamide)-chitosan	According to the study, Poly(N-isopropyl acrylamide)-chitosan may be employed to create an effective thermosensitive <i>in situ</i> gel based formulation for ophthalmic drug administration. The bioavailability, potency, and compliance of various eye drugs could be improved by it.	20

Conclusion: There are several ways that have been developed to deal with the difficulties in ocular drug delivery. The majority of these studies focus on *in-situ* gelling systems as potential solutions to the issues with standard ophthalmic preparation and to provide sustained drug release rates with better ocular bioavailability, therapeutic response while lowering systemic absorption and toxic effects. *In-situ* gel may also increase patient compliance because of its capacity to retain release rate and reduce the frequency of delivery. Various stimuli-sensitized polymers with high susceptibility to variations in pH, ion concentration or temperature are employed in *in-situ* gel formulations. Utilizing polymeric *in situ* gels for the regulated release of

different drugs has a number of benefits over traditional dosing forms. This study has helped us to better grasp the potentiality of polymers based thermosensitive in situ gel formulations. Despite the gel's incredible potential for ocular drug delivery only a few drugs in the in-situ gel form are presently being used in clinical application. In light of this, more research is needed to examine this drug delivery strategy for the clinical use of varieties of ophthalmic drugs.

Reference:

1. O.V. Khutoryanskaya, Z.A. Mayeva, G.A. Mun, V.V. Khutoryanskiy, *Biomacromolecules*. **2008**, *9*, 3353–3361.
2. B. Bhowmick, G. Sarkar, D. Rana, I. Roy, N.R. Saha, S. Ghosh, M. Bhowmik, D. Chattopadhyay, *RSC Adv*. **2015**, *5*, 60386–60391.
3. H. Qi, W. Chen, C. Huang, L. Li, C. Chen, W. Li, C. Wu, *Int. J. Pharm.* 2007, *337*, 178–187.
4. Y. Dong, P. Dong, D. Huang, L. Mei, Y. Xia, Z. Wang, X. Pan, G. Li, C. Wu, *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* **2015**, *9*, 182–90.
5. M. Ali, M.E. Byrne, *Expert Rev. Clin. Pharmacol.* **2008**, *1*, 145–161.
6. S.B. Makwana, V.A. Patel, S.J. Parmar, *Result Pharma Sci.* **2016**, *6*, 1–6.
7. C. Nagesh, M. Patil, S. Chandrashekhara, R. Sutar, *Der Pharm. Lett.* **2012**, *4*, 821–827.
8. J. C. Keister, E. R. Cooper, P.J. Missel, J.C. Lang, D.F. Huger. *J. Pharm. Sci.* **1991**, *80*, 50-3.
9. K. S. Anseth, C. N. Bowman, L. Brannon-Peppas, *Biomaterials*. **1996**, *17*, 1647–1657.
10. H. Huang, X. Qi, Y. Chen, Z. Wu, *Soudi Pharm. J.* **2019**, *27*, 990-999.
11. R.T. Pijls, et al. *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* **2005**, *59*, 283–288.
12. W. Kubu, Y. Konno, S. Miyazaki, D. Attwood, *Drug Development and Industrial Pharmacy*. **2004**, *30*, 593-599.
13. L. Liu, Q. Gao, X. Lu, H. Zhou, *Asian j. Pharm. Sci.* **2016**, *11*, 673–683.
14. A. Fakhari, J. A. Subramony. *J. Control Rel.* **2015**, *220*, 465–475.
15. S. Kempe, K. Mader, *J Control Rel.* **2012**, *161*, 668–679.

16. H. Almeida, M. H. Amaral, P. Lobao, J. M. S. Lobo, *Drug Discovery Today*, **2014**, 19, 400–412.
17. X. Wang, G. Liu, J. Ma, S. Guo, L. Gao, Y. Zia, X. Li, Q. Zhang. *Crit. Rev. Ther. Drug Carrier Syst.* **2013**, 30, 411–434.
18. NKhan, MAqil, SS Imam, A. Ali, *Pharm Dev Technol.*, **2015**, 20 (6): 662-9.
19. SRDevasani, ADev, SRathod, G.Deshmukh *Pharmaceutical and Biological Evaluations.* **2016**, 3 (1): 60-9.
20. YCao, CZhang, WShen, ZCheng, LLYu, QPing, *J Control Release.* **2007**, 120 (3), 186-194.
21. RSheshala, Y.YKok, J.MNng, R.RThakur, K. Dua, *Recent Pat Drug Deliv Formul.* **2015**, 9 (3), 237-48.
22. D. Jain, V. Kumar, S. Sing, A. Mullertz, D. Barshalom, *J Anal Pharm Res.* **2016**, 2, 00022.
23. S. S. Suryawanshi, H. K. Kunjwani, V. J. Kawade, A. M. Alkunte, J. D. Yadav. *Int. J. Res. Pharm. Sci.* **2012**, 2, 67-83.
24. T. S. Tinu, L. Thomas, A. B. Kumar, *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res.* **2013**, 20, 176-183.
25. P. R. Kute, S. B. Gondkar, R. B. Saudagar, *World J. Pharmacy Pharm, Sci.* **2015**, 4, 549-568.
26. G. Rajoria, A. Gupta, *Am. J. PharmTech Res.* **2012**, 2(4), 24-53.
27. M. Dewan, G. Sarkar, M. Bhowmik, B. Dasa, A. K. Chattoapadhyay, D. Rana, D. Chattopadhyay, *Int. J. of Bio. Macro.* **2017**, 102, 258–265
28. H. Almeida, M.H.Amaral, P.Lobao, J.M.Sousa Lobo. *Expert Opin Drug Deliv.* **2013**; 10 (9), 1223-37.
29. Y.Zambito, G.DColo. *InTech*, **2011**; 253-80.
30. K.Pal, A.TPaulson, D.Rousseau. (ed. Ebnesajjad S). Elsevier, 2013; 347-8.
31. JLi, HLiu, LLLiu, CNCai, HXXin, WLi. *Chem Pharm Bull (Tokyo)*. **2014**, 62 (10), 1000-8.
32. KAl-Khateb, E. KOzhmukhametova, M.NMussin, S.KSeilkhanov, T.KRakhypbekov, W.MLau, *et al.. Int J Pharm.* **2016**, 502 (1-2), 70-9.
33. NMorsi, DGhorab, HRefai, HTeba. *Int J Pharm.* **2016**, 506 (1-2), 57-67.

34. M. K. Bain, D. Maity, B. Bhowmick, D. Mondal, Md. M. R. Mollick, G. Sarkar, M. Bhowmik, D. Rana and D. Chattopadhyay, *Carbohydr. Polym.*, **2013**, **91**(2), 529–536.
35. M.K. Bain, M. Bhowmik, D. Maity, N.K. Bera, S. Ghosh and D. Chattopadhyay, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, **2010**, 118(2), 631–637.
36. M. K. Bain, B. Bhowmick, D. Maity, D. Momdal, Md. M. R. Mollick, B. K. Paul, M. Bhowmik, D. Rana and D. Chattopadhyay, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*, **2012**, 50(3), 565–572.
37. T.Gratieri, G.MGelfuso, E.MRocha, V.HSarmiento, Ode-Freitas, RFLopez. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm.* **2010**,75(2), 186-93.
38. L. Mayol, F. Quaglia, A. Borzacchiello, L. Ambrosia and M. I. La Rotonda, *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.*, **2008**, 70(1), 199–206.
39. G.HHsiue, S.HHsu, C.CYang, S.HLee, I.KYang. *Biomaterials.* **2002**, 23 (2):457-62.
40. M. Dewan, B. Bhowmik, G. Sarkar, D. Rana, M. K. Bain, M. Bhowmik and D. Chattopadhyay, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*,**2015**, **72**, 706–710.
41. M. Bhowmik, P. Kumari, G. Sarkar, M. K. Bain, B. Bhowmick, Md. M. R. Mollick. D. Mondal, D. Maity, D. Rana, D.Bhattacharjee and D. Chattopadhyay, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*, **2013**, 62, 117–123.
42. M. K. Bain, M. Bhowmik, S. N. Ghosh, D. Chattopadhyay, *J. Appl. Pol. Sci.*,**2009**, 113, 1241-1246.
43. S. Miyazaki, F. Suisha, A. Kawasaki, M. Shirakawa, K. Yamatoya, D. Attwood. Thermally reversible xyloglucan gels as vehicles for rectal drug delivery. *J Control Release*,1998, 56, 75-83.

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